

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Zuhriddinov Hayotbek Qaxramonjon o'g'li

**ERGONOMIC PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS THROUGH
DIGITALIZATION OF MODERN EDUCATION**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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